

ISic1151

I.Sicily inscription 1151

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone(grey)

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 136

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ὀπερηία Λητώι, Μου
2. σαίου γυνήι χαῖρε χρησ
3. τή καὶ εὐσεβής

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492764

EDCS 39102308

PHI 140636

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio*

et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV. Berlin.
At 14.0332 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
Brugnone, A. 1974. Iscrizione greche del museo civico di Termini Imerese.
Kokalos. 20: 218-264. At 13

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1151. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351651>

Photo J. Prag, courtesy Museo civico di Termini Imerese